

ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF REGULATORY COMPLIANCE INDICATORS ON DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS' PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between regulatory compliance and the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2013 to 2023, using return on assets (ROA) as the performance measure. It focuses on four compliance indicators: regulatory contraventions, unresolved customer complaints, litigation claims, and penalties or fines. Using secondary data from banks' annual reports and a panel data approach with ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation, supported by unit root and descriptive analyses, the results show that contraventions, complaints, and penalties do not have a significant effect on ROA. In contrast, litigation claims exert a significant negative impact, indicating that legal exposures materially reduce profitability. The study concludes that enforcement mechanisms need strengthening and recommends stricter regulatory sanctions alongside the establishment of effective compliance units within banks to ensure adherence to regulatory standards.

KEYWORDS

Regulatory Compliance; Financial Performance; Return on Assets; Litigation Claims; Deposit Money Banks

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian banking sector plays a central role in economic development, with deposit money banks serving as key intermediaries that mobilise savings and extend credit to households, businesses, and government, thereby supporting investment, financial inclusion, and poverty reduction (Adegbite, 2020; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). However, the ability of banks to perform these functions effectively depends on the stability, transparency, and integrity of the financial system, which is largely sustained through regulatory compliance. The Nigerian banking industry over a period of time has undergone significant reforms aimed at strengthening its resilience and aligning it with global standards. These include risk-based supervision, Basel II and III capital requirements, Know Your Customer (KYC) policies, anti-money laundering frameworks, and enhanced

corporate governance codes. Regulatory bodies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria, the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria have been central in implementing these reforms to strengthen oversight and protect depositors (CBN, 2021; NDIC, 2022). Owing to its critical role in the financial system, the banking sector is highly regulated, and compliance is mandatory. Non-compliance typically attracts sanctions ranging from monetary penalties to operational restrictions. Globally, regulatory fines have significantly affected banks' profitability and lending capacity (Slater, 2015). In Nigeria, similar outcomes are evident, as seen in the ₦2.978 billion fines imposed by the CBN in 2015 for violations of Treasury Single Account directives (CBN, 2016).

Despite these measures, Nigerian banks continue to experience challenges such as fraud, weak internal controls, operational inefficiencies, and regulatory breaches. Infractions including foreign exchange violations, inaccurate reporting, and failure to meet prudential standards have attracted sanctions and raised concerns about systemic risk (Okere & Muideen, 2018; NDIC, 2022). While compliance is essential, it also imposes costs through audit requirements, reporting obligations, and technology investments, as well as indirect costs such as reduced flexibility in decision-making.

Existing studies such as Akonye, Okonkwo, and Okoye (2019) highlight persistent regulatory violations among deposit money banks, despite the existence of several legal and institutional frameworks, including the Banking Ordinance of 1952, the CBN Acts of 1958 and 2007, the NDIC Act of 2006, and BOFIA and its amendments. Although these frameworks have strengthened supervision, issues such as regulatory overlap, weak coordination among agencies, and inconsistent enforcement continue to limit their effectiveness.

Consequently, cases of non-compliance, unresolved customer complaints, litigation exposures, and episodes of financial distress still persist in the banking sector. These realities raise concerns about the effectiveness of current enforcement mechanisms and the underlying causes of regulatory violations. Against this background, this study examines the factors driving non-compliance among deposit money banks, evaluates its impact on financial performance, and assesses how regulatory sanctions influence banking behaviour and outcomes.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Regulatory compliance and the performance of deposit money banks remain a recurring concern in Nigeria's banking sector. These institutions are central to financial intermediation, supporting savings mobilisation, credit creation, employment generation, and overall economic growth, thereby contributing significantly to GDP and national development (Olaoye, 2015; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). However, their ability to sustain these developmental roles is often constrained by persistent issues such as weak corporate governance, insider abuse, financial misreporting, corruption, and gaps in regulatory oversight (Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, 2022).

The Nigerian banking system operates under a multi-regulatory framework involving agencies such as the Central Bank of Nigeria, Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, the Corporate Affairs Commission, the Securities and Exchange Commission, and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria. While this arrangement is intended to strengthen supervision and ensure financial stability, it often results in regulatory overlap and coordination challenges that may weaken enforcement effectiveness (Sanusi, 2012; NDIC, 2022). In response to violations, regulators impose sanctions including monetary fines, operational restrictions, and in severe cases, licence revocation. Although these measures are designed to promote discipline, they may also impose financial and reputational burdens that affect profitability, investor confidence, and long-term sustainability (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021; Okere & Muideen, 2018).

Notwithstanding continuous reforms and enforcement efforts, non-compliance issues such as unresolved customer complaints, litigation risks, and operational inefficiencies remain prevalent in the sector. This raises concerns about how effective regulatory compliance mechanisms are in influencing bank performance, particularly whether compliance-related factors such as contraventions, complaints, litigation exposures, and penalties have measurable effects on financial outcomes. Against this backdrop, the study examines the relationship between regulatory compliance and the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, focusing on return on assets as the key performance indicator. It investigates whether regulatory breaches, unresolved complaints, litigation claims, and fines significantly affect profitability.

Generally, the study tests the hypotheses that compliance indicators do not significantly influence return on assets, while empirically assessing whether these regulatory and operational factors independently affect the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Deposit money banks are central to financial intermediation in Nigeria, mobilising deposits and extending credit to households, firms, and government, thereby supporting investment, job creation, and economic growth (Ibrahim & Lawal, 2019; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). Their ability to sustain these functions depends on sound regulation, governance, and compliance, as well as effective management of risks and resources.

Bank performance is commonly assessed through indicators such as return on assets, return on equity, and net interest margin, with return on assets widely preferred because it captures efficiency in generating profit from total assets (Eze & Okoye, 2020; Hassan & Bashir, 2016). Beyond profitability, performance also reflects liquidity, credit creation, and overall financial stability. Liquidity ensures banks can meet short-term obligations, while credit to the private sector reflects their role in supporting economic activity (Olaoye & Adeyemi, 2021; World Bank, 2022).

Risk management and corporate governance are fundamental to banking stability. Risk management involves identifying and controlling credit, liquidity, market, operational, and regulatory risks, while corporate governance ensures accountability through board oversight and transparent decision-making. In Nigeria, reforms following past banking crises have strengthened governance expectations and regulatory supervision to improve stability and investor confidence (Sanusi, 2012; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). The OECD also emphasizes that strong governance improves financial discipline and institutional resilience.

Compliance is another core element of banking operations, requiring adherence to laws, regulations, and internal policies. Although compliance involves costs such as audits, reporting systems, and training, it reduces legal risk, fraud, and reputational damage when effectively implemented (Alley, 2022; Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2021). Increasingly, scholars argue that compliance should be embedded in organizational culture, supported by strong leadership and independent oversight functions such as Chief Compliance Officers (Beebejaun, 2022; Prorokowski & Prorokowski, 2017).

The relationship between compliance and financial performance is complex. While compliance increases operational costs, it can enhance long-term stability and profitability by improving risk management and preventing regulatory sanctions. Empirical evidence shows that Nigerian banks with stronger compliance frameworks tend to perform better over time due to improved efficiency and reduced exposure to penalties (Okezie & Okereke, 2023). Conversely, repeated non-compliance can lead to fines, litigation costs, and reputational damage, weakening profitability and investor confidence (Yusuf & Ekundayo, 2018).

Despite regulatory reforms, Nigerian banks continue to face compliance challenges, including governance weaknesses, fraud, and regulatory breaches, as illustrated by past banking failures linked to poor oversight and insider abuse (Kasum & Etudaiye-Muthar, 2016; NDIC, 2019). In response, regulators such as the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria have introduced stronger governance codes and enforcement frameworks to improve accountability and system stability (CBN, 2019; Ahmed & Calice, 2022).

Within this framework, regulatory non-compliance charges serve as enforcement tools, covering both operational and governance violations. Operational breaches relate to failures in reporting, AML controls, and internal processes, while governance-related charges arise from board-level failures and policy violations. According to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2021), these fall under operational risk and can significantly affect institutional performance.

Overall, the literature suggests that although compliance imposes short-term costs, it plays a crucial role in reducing risk, strengthening governance, and enhancing long-term financial performance. In the Nigerian banking sector, improving compliance culture and regulatory enforcement remains essential for sustaining stability and profitability in deposit money banks.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two complementary theoretical perspectives of compliance and complexity theory, and shareholder value maximisation theory which together explain how regulatory requirements interact with banking performance in a complex financial environment. The evidences are buttressed in the works of (Anderson, 1999; Daft, 1992; Galbraith, 1982; Miledová & Nemcová, 2009; De Andres & Vallelado, 2008; Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2021

In contrast, shareholder value maximisation theory (Friedman, 1970) argues that firms exist primarily to maximise shareholder wealth within legal and ethical boundaries. In banking, this is reflected in indicators such as return on assets and return on equity, which measure how effectively resources are used to generate profit (Brigham & Daves, 2004). From this perspective, compliance-related costs such as fines, penalties, and regulatory enforcement, reduce distributable profits and may limit value creation if not properly managed.

Empirical Framework

Empirical studies present mixed but informative evidence. Studies such as Okoi and Ocheni (2014) and Ene and Bello (2016) show that stronger governance structures tend to improve bank performance in Nigeria, while Ikpefan and Ojeka (2017) suggest that governance alone may not fully prevent financial distress, highlighting implementation gaps. Globally, studies such as Armour, Mayer, and Polo (2015) and Hodgson (2017) demonstrate that regulatory sanctions can significantly reduce firm value through both financial and reputational losses. Similarly, Koster and Pelster (2017) find that penalties may even increase systemic risk in large banks.

In Nigeria, findings are also mixed. Ismaila and Damola (2018) report that regulatory penalties may not significantly affect profitability due to their relatively low cost, while Akonye, Okonkwo, and Okoye (2019) find that compliance charges negatively affect performance when measured through return on equity. More broadly, Almaw (2020) concludes that the impact of regulation depends on context, with prudential rules improving stability but overly stringent regulations potentially constraining profitability.

Generally, the literature shows that while governance and compliance generally support better banking performance, the effect of regulatory sanctions varies depending on enforcement strength and institutional context.

Gap in Empirical Literature

A review of existing studies also reveals important gaps. Much of the Nigerian literature focuses on identifying regulatory breaches and penalties (Abioye, 2017; Ismaila & Damola, 2018) without clearly linking compliance indicators to financial performance measures such as return on assets or shareholder value. In addition, compliance is often framed as a cost rather than a strategic tool that may enhance risk management and long-term sustainability, despite global evidence suggesting otherwise (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2021). There is also limited firm-level analysis, with most studies adopting aggregated sector-wide approaches that overlook differences across banks. Finally, little attention has been given to the post-2016 regulatory reforms and how they may have reshaped the compliance–performance relationship in Nigeria. These gaps highlight the need for further empirical investigation into whether regulatory compliance acts as a constraint or a driver of performance among deposit money banks in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The model specification for this study is grounded in the panel data framework, designed to capture the relationship between regulatory compliance indicators and the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The approach draws inspiration from Yusuf and Ekundayo (2018), who employed both disaggregated and aggregated models to examine the impact of banking infractions on performance outcomes. Their framework distinguishes between different categories of regulatory breaches while also providing a simplified aggregate representation of total penalties and their effect on performance. Their model is stated as follows:

Disaggregated model

$$PERF_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 BCGAP_{it} + \beta_2 FREAE_{it} + \beta_3 BARBO_{it} + \beta_4 CARM_{it} + \beta_5 BRPCC_{it} + \beta_6 FOREXIT_{it} + \beta_7 TSAPSD_{it} + \beta_8 AMLKYC_{it} + \beta_9 OERS_{it} + \beta_{10} TA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Aggregated model

$$PERF_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 TotalPen_{it} + \beta_2 TA_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- PERF = Performance variable.
- BCGAP = Breach of Corporate Governance and CBN Appointment and Promotion Guidelines.
- FREAE = Financial Reporting, External Auditing And External Examination Related Infractions.
- BARBO = Breach of Banking Activities Regulations, Branch Operations Guidelines and Investment Guidelines.
- CARM = Credit and Risk Management Infractions.
- BEPC = Breach of electronic payment regulations and customer complaints.
- FOREXIT = Foreign exchange and international trade related infractions.
- TSAPSD = Non-compliance with TSA and public sector deposit guidelines and Related infractions.
- AMLKYC = Noncompliance with AML/CFT regulations and KYC principles.
- OERS = others (not included in any of the above).
- TA = Total Assets.
- TotalPen = Total Penalties.

Following from the above model, this study used an aggregated model stated as follows:

$$ROA = f(NCN, NCB, LIT, ACT, \quad (3)$$

Where:

- ROA = Return on assets as proxy for performance
- NCN = Total number of contraventions
- NCB = Total number of unresolved complaint
- LIT = Total amount of claims for litigation
- ACT = Total penalty/fine paid for contraventions
- ACB = Total amount Claimed of Unresolved Complaints escalated to CBN for intervention
- f = sign of functional relation

The econometric form of the model is presented as:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NCN_{it} + \beta_2 NCB_{it} + \beta_3 NLOGLIT_{it} + \beta_4 LOGACT_{it} + \beta_5 LOGACB_{it} + u_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where:

- t = Time series property,
- i = Cross-section property,
- u_{it} = Error term
- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1 to β_5 = Coefficients

The *a priori* expectations of the models are: $\beta_0 > 0$, $\beta_1 < 0$, $\beta_2 < 0$, $\beta_3 < 0$, $\beta_4 < 0$, $\beta_5 < 0$.

Method of Data Analyses

The data analysis procedure for the study follows a structured econometric approach. Descriptive statistics are first used to summarize the characteristics of the dataset and assess its distributional properties. Correlation analysis is then employed to examine the relationships among variables and to detect potential multicollinearity issues. Unit root tests are conducted to ensure the stationarity of the data series, which is essential for reliable panel estimation. The Hausman test is subsequently applied to determine whether a fixed effects or random effects model is more appropriate for the analysis. Finally, the panel least squares technique is used to estimate the model and evaluate the impact of regulatory compliance variables on bank performance, thereby providing empirical answers to the research hypotheses.

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Results from descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, unit root test, Hausman test and panel least square. Are presented and analyzed

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics with Common Sample on Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

	ROA	NCN	NCB	LOGLIT	LOGACT	LOGACB
Mean	0.673782	5.266667	8897.693	9.798412	7.477377	8.753694
Median	0.017754	4.000000	188.0000	9.842988	7.477121	8.966888
Maximum	9.327363	22.000000	220904.0	12.85309	9.472581	11.37233
Minimum	-0.019498	1.000000	2.000000	7.697465	5.462398	4.947924
Std. Dev.	2.248894	3.362485	31557.81	1.339366	0.638196	1.374411
Skewness	3.185099	2.083852	5.200684	0.432964	0.189678	-0.702555

Kurtosis	11.32691	9.678402	31.78138	2.318814	4.016825	3.305279
Jarque-Bera	343.4904	193.6588	2926.738	3.793266	3.680759	6.461027
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.150073	0.158757	0.039537
Sum	50.53368	395.0000	667327.0	734.8809	560.8033	656.5270
Sum Sq. Dev.	374.2569	836.6667	7.37E+10	132.7487	30.13976	139.7865
Observations	75	75	75	75	75	75

Source: Author’s Estimation from Eview 10, 2025.

Where:

ROA: Return on Assets

NCN: Non-Compliance Charges/Penalties

NCB: Number of Compliance Notices

LOGLIT: Log of Liquidity

LOGACT: Log of Assets

LOGACB: Log of Capital Base

The descriptive statistics in Table 4.1 provide an overview of the distribution and behaviour of the study variables. Return on assets (ROA), used as a measure of performance, has an average value of 0.67, indicating that Nigerian deposit money banks generated less than 1% return on assets on average between 2013 and 2023. However, the wide gap between the maximum (9.33) and minimum (-0.02) values points to significant differences in performance across banks. The relatively high standard deviation (2.25) and strong positive skewness (3.18) further suggest that only a few banks recorded exceptionally high returns, while the majority experienced modest or low performance.

The compliance indicators also reveal notable patterns. The average number of compliance notices (NCN) is 5.27, with a maximum of 22, indicating that banks frequently encounter regulatory issues, although the median value of 4 shows that most banks recorded fewer notices. Non-compliance charges (NCB) have a mean of 8,897.69, but the very high maximum value of 220,904 highlights that some banks incurred substantial penalties. The high skewness (5.20) and kurtosis (31.78) confirm that these penalties are unevenly distributed, with a few banks accounting for extreme values.

The control variables; log of liquidity (LOGLIT), log of assets (LOGACT), and log of capital base (LOGACB), display more stability, with mean values of 9.79, 7.48, and 8.75 respectively, and relatively lower skewness. Liquidity and asset levels show moderate variation, while capital base appears closer to a normal distribution. This is supported by the Jarque-Bera test, which indicates that LOGLIT and LOGACT are approximately normally distributed (p-values of 0.15 and 0.16), whereas ROA, NCN, and NCB deviate significantly from normality at the 1% level.

Generally, the results suggest that compliance challenges are persistent among Nigerian banks, with penalties varying widely in magnitude. These patterns indicate that compliance issues may play an important role in shaping differences in bank performance.

Correlation Analysis

Descriptive Statistics on Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Table 4.2 Correlation Results on Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary

Date: 01/05/25 Time: 17:12

Sample: 2013 2023

Included observations: 75

Balanced sample (listwise missing value deletion)

Correlation

Probability	ROA	NCN	NCB	LOGLIT	LOGACT	LOGACB
ROA	1.000000 -----					
NCN	-0.113492 0.3323	1.000000 -----				
NCB	-0.080321 0.4933	0.105604 0.3672	1.000000 -----			
LOGLIT	-0.254379 0.0276	0.113832 0.3308	-0.065309 0.5777	1.000000 -----		
LOGACT	-0.226264 0.0509	0.412960 0.0002	0.280928 0.0146	0.161653 0.1659	1.000000 -----	
LOGACB	-0.174448 0.1344	-0.146850 0.2087	0.198419 0.0879	2.58E-05 0.9998	0.074169 0.5271	1.000000 -----

Source: Author’s Estimation from EView 10, 2025.

The correlation analysis in Table 4.2 provides initial insights into the relationship between compliance indicators and bank performance (ROA). ROA is negatively related to the total number of contraventions (NCN = -0.11) and unresolved complaints (NCB = -0.08), but both relationships are statistically insignificant (p-values > 0.3), indicating a weak and inconclusive link between these compliance measures and profitability.

In contrast, ROA shows a negative and statistically significant relationship with litigation claims (LOGLIT: $r = -0.25$, $p = 0.028$), suggesting that higher litigation exposure significantly reduces profitability. ROA is also negatively associated with penalties (LOGACT: $r = -0.23$, $p = 0.051$), significant at the 10% level, implying that increased penalties or related factors may moderately reduce returns. Similarly, ROA has a negative but insignificant relationship with LOGACB (-0.17 , $p = 0.13$), indicating that higher capital-related measures do not necessarily improve profitability.

Among the independent variables, NCN and NCB are weakly and positively related (0.11), while NCN has a strong positive correlation with LOGACT (0.41, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that banks with more contraventions tend to incur higher penalties. LOGACT is also moderately correlated with NCB (0.28, $p = 0.015$), and LOGLIT shows a weak positive relationship with LOGACT (0.16).

The results indicate that compliance-related factors generally have a negative but modest relationship with bank performance, while firm-specific characteristics such as size, liquidity, and capital structure appear to play a more influential role in determining profitability.

Unit Root Analysis

Correlation Results on Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Table 4.3 Unit Root Result on Series for Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Variable (Series)	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	Prob.	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	Prob.	PP - Fisher Chi-square	Prob.	Remark
ROA	-72.8646	0.0000	66.8681	0.0001	103.247	0.0000	I(0)
NCN	-2.27275	0.0115	23.0253	0.6315	26.3432	0.4444	
D(NCN)	-8.73335	0.0000	82.6384	0.0000	151.988	0.0000	I(1)
NCB	-1.26325	0.1032	26.8017	0.3138	32.8340	0.1076	
D(NCB)	-8.73335	0.0000	82.6384	0.0000	151.988	0.0000	I(1)
LOGLIT	-1.26325	0.1032	26.8017	0.3138	32.8340	0.1076	
D(LOGLIT)	-9.75385	0.0000	74.5093	0.0000	110.548	0.0000	I(1)
LOGACT	-2.07385	0.0190	16.9116	0.7682	4.87466	1.0000	
D(LOGACT)	-8.12239	0.0000	66.1726	0.0000	116.407	0.0000	I(1)
LOGACB	-2.07385	0.0190	16.9116	0.7682	4.87466	1.0000	
D(LOGACB)	-7.83444	0.0000	56.8560	0.0000	96.3119	0.0000	I(1)

Source: Author’s Estimation from EView 10, 2025.

The unit root results in Table 4.3 assess the stationarity of the variables using the Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC), Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF–Fisher), and Phillips-Perron (PP–Fisher) tests. Stationarity is essential to avoid spurious regression by ensuring constant mean and variance over time.

The findings show that ROA is stationary at level (I (0), as all tests report significant values ($p < 0.05$), meaning no differencing is required. In contrast, NCN and NCB are non-stationary at level (e.g., NCN: ADF = 0.6315, PP = 0.4444; NCB: $p > 0.1$), but both become stationary after first differencing D(NCN),D(NCB)D(NCN), D(NCB)D(NCN),D(NCB) with strong significance ($p < 0.01$), indicating they are **I(1)** variables.

Similarly, LOGLIT is non-stationary at level (ADF = 0.3138, PP = 0.1076) but becomes stationary after differencing ($p < 0.01$), confirming I(1). LOGACT and LOGACB show mixed results at level (e.g., LLC $p = 0.0190$ vs ADF and PP > 0.7), but both achieve strong stationarity after first differencing ($p < 0.01$), and are therefore also I (1).

The results conclusively indicate a mixed order of integration, with ROA as I(0) and all other variables (NCN, NCB, LOGLIT, LOGACT, LOGACB) as I(1). This combination is appropriate for panel regression analysis and supports the possibility of examining long-run relationships between compliance indicators and bank performance

Regression Analysis

In determining which of the regression effect is more suitable for analysis, we conduct the Hausman test. Using the 5% level of statistical significance, the probability value of the Hausman test is 0.0358 which is less than 5% implying that the fixed effect panel least square is more appropriate for testing the hypotheses for the study.

Table 4.4: Hausman Test for Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test				
Equation: Untitled				
Test period random effects				
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random		11.928059	5	0.0358
** WARNING: estimated period random effects variance is zero.				

Source: Author’s Estimation from EView 10, 2025.

Result in table 4.4 revealed that The model incorporated fixed effects with period dummies to account for time-specific influences. The results show that the constant term (C) is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level (coefficient = 4.6684, $p = 0.0007$). This implies that, in the absence of compliance-related factors, banks maintain a baseline positive level of profitability.

The coefficient is negative (-0.0572) but statistically insignificant ($p = 0.3302$). This suggests that increases in compliance notices do not have a meaningful impact on profitability. The coefficient is extremely small and insignificant ($p = 0.5671$), indicating that the direct count of breaches does not significantly explain variations in ROA.

This variable is negative (-0.1993) and statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.0095$). This indicates that higher litigation levels adversely affect banks’ performance, reducing ROA. The coefficient is negative (-0.1048) but not statistically significant ($p = 0.3110$). This suggests that administrative sanctions may reduce performance, but the effect is not strong enough to be conclusive.

This variable is negative (-0.1061) and statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0226$). It implies that frequent administrative breaches reduce financial performance, demonstrating the burden of non-compliance on profitability. In terms of model fit, the weighted R-squared is 0.2035, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.0177. This indicates that compliance variables collectively explain about 20% of the variation in banks’ financial performance, though the explanatory power reduces significantly after adjusting for degrees of freedom. The F-statistic (1.0950) is insignificant ($p = 0.3806$), suggesting that the model as a whole does not strongly explain variations in ROA.

The Durbin-Watson statistic (0.5243) is relatively low, pointing to the possible presence of serial correlation in the residuals, which could affect the efficiency of the estimates.

The regression analysis reveals that litigation (LOGLIT) and administrative compliance breaches (LOGACB) are the main compliance-related factors that significantly reduce the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Other variables such as compliance notices and breaches show negative but statistically insignificant effects. Overall, the findings emphasize that non-compliance, particularly when it results in litigation and administrative sanctions, undermines bank performance.

Table 4.5: Panel Least Square Result for Compliance and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: ROA				
Method: Panel EGLS (Period weights)				
Date: 01/05/25 Time: 17:01				
Sample (adjusted): 2013- 2023				
Periods included: 10				
Cross-sections included: 11				
Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 75				
Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix				
Period weights (PCSE) standard errors & covariance (d.f. corrected)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.668412	1.302357	3.584588	0.0007
NCN	-0.057160	0.058231	-0.981606	0.3302
NCB	-3.20E-06	5.57E-06	-0.575513	0.5671
LOGLIT	-0.199287	0.074373	-2.679559	0.0095
LOGACT	-0.104824	0.102595	-1.021730	0.3110
LOGACB	-0.106078	0.045315	-2.340885	0.0226
	Effects Specification			
Period fixed (dummy variables)				
	Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.203509	Mean dependent var		0.567642
Adjusted R-squared	0.017662	S.D. dependent var		1.837190
S.E. of regression	1.889502	Sum squared resid		214.2132
F-statistic	1.095032	Durbin-Watson stat		0.524330
Prob(F-statistic)	0.380612			
	Unweighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.223466	Mean dependent var		0.673782

Sum squared resid	290.6231	Durbin-Watson stat	0.289815
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Source: Author’s Estimation from EView 10, 2025.

The panel least squares results (Table 3.5) examine the relationship between compliance indicators and bank performance (ROA) using data from 2013–2023, covering 11 banks and 75 panel observations, with period fixed effects included.

The findings show that the constant term is positive and significant, indicating a baseline level of profitability even without compliance pressures. The number of compliance notices (NCN) has a negative but insignificant effect on ROA, while compliance breaches (NCB) show a near-zero and insignificant impact, suggesting limited influence on performance when considered individually.

On the other hand, litigation (LOGLIT) has a negative and statistically significant effect, confirming that legal costs substantially reduce profitability. Administrative charges (LOGACT) also have a negative but insignificant relationship with ROA, indicating only a weak impact. However, administrative compliance breaches (LOGACB) are negative and statistically significant, showing that repeated violations materially undermine bank performance.

In terms of model fit, the weighted R^2 is about 20%, indicating limited explanatory power, and the adjusted R^2 is even lower, reinforcing this weakness. The F-statistic is not significant, suggesting that the variables jointly do not strongly explain profitability. Additionally, a low Durbin-Watson statistic points to possible serial correlation.

The result demonstrate that while most compliance variables negatively relate to performance, only litigation and administrative breaches have significant effects, highlighting them as the most critical factors reducing profitability in Nigerian deposit money banks.

Test of Hypotheses

The study tested the hypotheses using regression results at a 5% significance level.

Hypothesis One examined whether the total number of contraventions significantly affects return on assets (ROA). The result shows a probability value of 0.3302, which is greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that contraventions do not have a statistically significant effect on ROA in Nigerian deposit money banks.

Hypothesis Two assessed the effect of unresolved customer complaints on ROA. With a probability value of 0.5671, which exceeds the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis was also accepted. This suggests that unresolved complaints do not significantly influence bank performance.

Hypothesis Three, the result revealed a probability value of 0.0096, which is less than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it was concluded that litigation claims have a significant negative effect on ROA, indicating that legal exposures materially reduce bank performance.

Hypothesis Four tested the effect of penalties and fines on ROA. With a probability value of 0.3110, the null hypothesis was accepted, implying that regulatory penalties do not significantly affect bank performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings show that the number of regulatory contraventions does not significantly influence bank performance, suggesting that it is not the frequency of violations but their nature and financial weight that matters. Evidence from industry cases supports this, where banks with fewer infractions sometimes incur higher penalties than those with more violations, indicating inconsistent sanctioning patterns. This reduces the deterrent effect of compliance enforcement.

Similarly, unresolved customer complaints were found to have no significant impact on performance. This may be explained by the relatively homogeneous nature of banking services in Nigeria, which limits customer mobility despite dissatisfaction. As a result, such complaints may affect customer sentiment but do not significantly alter banks' revenue streams.

In contrast, litigation exposure was found to significantly and negatively affect performance. This aligns with findings by Baucus and Baucus (2017) and Bhagat et al. (1998), who argue that legal actions damage firm reputation and reduce future business opportunities. Litigation therefore represents a more serious compliance consequence compared to other forms of regulatory breaches.

Interestingly, regulatory penalties were found not to significantly affect performance. This supports the view that some banks may internalize fines as operational costs, particularly when the perceived benefits of non-compliance outweigh the penalties incurred, consistent with Becker's (2015) economic deterrence argument. However, this contrasts with studies such as Seuraj and Watson (2016), which found that compliance improves financial performance.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Generally, the findings indicate a mixed relationship between regulatory compliance and bank performance. While most compliance indicators do not significantly affect return on assets, litigation stands out as the only variable with a strong negative effect. This suggests that some regulatory infractions may not immediately translate into financial consequences, potentially encouraging repeated non-compliance.

The study therefore concludes that regulatory sanctions in the Nigerian banking sector may not be sufficiently deterrent, as many banks appear to treat penalties as routine costs rather than corrective measures. This reflects weaknesses in enforcement and corporate governance structures.

It is recommended that regulatory authorities strengthen enforcement mechanisms by imposing stricter and more consequential penalties, including restrictions on banking licences for repeat offenders. Banks should also establish stronger compliance departments led by qualified officers to ensure full regulatory adherence. In addition, regulators should enforce periodic compliance reviews, restrict access to central banking facilities for persistent violators, and improve public disclosure of non-compliant banks to enhance transparency and market discipline.

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